

THE EFFECT OF BIOLOGICAL AND INANIMATE (PLASTIC) MULCHES ON PLANT DEVELOPMENT AND YIELD INCREASE OF TOMATO CV. NAVEEN 2000⁺ UNDER UTTARAKHAND HILLS

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ABSTRACT

A field trial was conducted at Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pithoragarh (Uttarakhand) during the summer session of 2024 and 2025 for the study “the effect of biological and inanimate (plastic) mulches on plant development and yield increase of Tomato Cv. Naveen 2000⁺ under Uttarakhand Hills”. The most common types of inorganic mulch are rocks or gravel, plastic, fabric and rubber sheets. Inorganic or inanimate mulches do not decompose. The most common types of biological mulch are compost, tree bark, wood chips, leaves, grass, pine needles, straw, sawdust, hulls etc. Biological mulches easily decompose and provide nutrients to plants. The experiment was laid out as Randomized Block Design (RBD) with five replications. The experiment includes eight treatments viz., T₁- Black polyethylene mulch (30 Microns), T₂- Silver polyethylene mulch (25 Microns), T₃- Pasture mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₄- Paddy straw mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₅- Wheat straw mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₆- Wild grass leaves mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₇- Grass leaves trash (which are used for the cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 ton hectare⁻¹ and T₈- Control (Without mulch). The result showed that the treatment T₁- Black polyethylene mulch (30 microns) was found to be best among the various mulch treatments and recorded higher values for plant height, days taken to first flowering, number of branches plant⁻¹, days taken to first harvesting and the treatment T₆- Wild grass leaves mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹) was found to be recorded higher values for fruit weight (gram), number of fruits plant⁻¹, fruit yield plant⁻¹ (kilogram), number of fruits cluster⁻¹, fruit yield plot⁻¹ (kilogram) and fruit yield hectare⁻¹ (ton).

KEYWORD: Mulch, Pasture, Trash, Un-irrigated, Biological, Inanimate.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is one of the most popular and widely grown vegetables and recognized as important commercial and dietary vegetable crops (Singh *et al.*, 2014). The tomato is the edible berry of the plant *Solanum lycopersicum* (*Encyclopaedia*, 2014), commonly known as the tomato plant. Fresh fruits of tomato are in great demand round the year and throughout the country (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). The species originated in Western South America, Mexico, and Central America (*Encyclopaedia*, 2018). Vegetables are said to be the best food for our body. Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) belongs to the Solanaceae family and is the second most important fruit or vegetable crop next to potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). It is cultivated for fresh fruit and

processed products. Tomatoes contain many health-promoting compounds including vitamins, carotenoids, and phenolic compounds. In addition to its economic and nutritional importance, tomatoes have become the model for the study of fleshy fruit development. Tomato is a climacteric fruit and dramatic metabolic changes occur during its fruit development. Tomatoes contain many health-promoting compounds and are easily integrated as a nutritious part of a balanced diet (Marti *et al.*, 2016). In addition to consuming the fresh fruits, consumers use tomatoes in processed products such as soups, juices and sauces (Krauss *et al.*, 2006 and Li *et al.*, 2018b). Over the last decade, consumers have become more aware of foods as a source of health benefits and their roles in prevention of several chronic diseases and dysfunctions

(Pem and Jeewon 2015). Although a wealth of functional foodstuffs have been created to fulfil these requirements, it is important to note that the consumption of “conventional foods” such as fruits and vegetables is more effective for this purpose (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2014).

The practice of applying mulch for the production of vegetables is thousands of years old. To increase the production per unit area, the use of mulch is one of the suitable methods. Mulching is an agricultural cropping technique that involves placing organic or synthetic materials on soil around plants to provide a more favourable environment for growth and production. There are different types of mulch used in the field depending on the purpose of mulch. Mulches are used to control soil temperature, safe guard plant roots from heat, prevent soil evaporation, retain soil moisture, prevent weed growth, improve water use efficiency and affect the microclimate of the soil. By creating unfavourable conditions for weed seed germination and acting as a physical barrier for emerging weeds, mulches limit weed growth. A good mulch layer can save many hours of laborious weeding. In light of the above importance, the present experiment was carried out to study the effect of different type of mulches on growth and yield of tomato.

The practice of mulching has been utilized to great advantage in the development of horticultural crops (Smolikowski *et al.*, 2001) and has been proven to significantly improve the growing conditions of vegetables. Mulch is any material placed on the soil surface to conserve moisture, maintain favourable soil temperatures around plant roots prevent erosion and reduce weed growth, which results in better plant growth and development. Soil mulching is a method used in crops grown around the world, especially for vegetables, which can promote numerous advantages. Mulching improves soil water retention capacity, contributes to early crop development, changes the soil temperature and reduces weed incidence, and all these factors contribute to increased yield (Mutetwa and Mtaita, 2014 and Haque *et al.*, 2018). The mulching can be done with organic materials such as straw or with inorganic materials such as plastic films. The choice of mulching material depends on the climate, the cost-benefit ratio, and the crop to be grown (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Mulching materials have a direct influence on the microclimate near the plant, which can have positive or negative impacts on plant physiological metabolism (Kader *et al.*, 2017). Beneficial effects of soil mulching have been reported for several crops, including tomato (Kosterna, 2014) and maize (Wang *et al.*, 2019). Mulches can be derived from either organic or inorganic materials (Rao *et al.*, 2016). The colour of mulch determines its energy-radiating behaviour and its influence on the microclimate around the vegetable plant. Colour determines the surface temperature of the mulch and the underlying soil temperatures. On the use of plastic mulches for vegetable

production was to define the impact differently coloured mulches had on soil temperature, moisture retention, and vegetable yields (Rao *et al.*, 2016). Mulching has also been identified by many workers as a method to provide a favourable soil environment by minimizing crusting at the soil surface and keep it stable (Tipu *et al.*, 2014).

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present research work entitled “the effect of biological and in animate mulches on plant development and yield of tomato under Uttarakhand Hills Cv. 2000⁺” was carried out in the summer of 2024 and 2025 at the Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pithoragarh (Uttarakhand). The farm is geographically area lies between 30°15’ North latitude and 78°30’ East longitude at an altitude of 1950 m at KVK, Gaina, Pithoragarh (GBPUA&T, Pantnagar). The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) in eight treatments and five replications. The treatment consists of: T₁- Black polyethylene mulch (30 Microns), T₂- Silver polyethylene mulch (25 Microns), T₃- Pasture mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₄- Paddy straw mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₅- Wheat straw mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₆- Wild grass leaves mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹), T₇- Grass leaves trash (which are used for the cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 ton hectare⁻¹ and T₈- Control (Without mulch). Mulches were spread in the plot prior a day of transplanting as per treatment. Plastic mulch was laid by cutting into pieces of 2×3 m to cover the plot area. For the seedlings, transplanting holes were made in plastic at 50×30 cm spacing. After that, all sides of the mulch sheet were anchored at 15 cm depth of soil. Paddy straw, wheat straw, wild grass leaves and grass leaves trash mulch of 15 cm thickness were spread in the plot. The recommended doses of fertilizers were applied. To raise a healthy crop, all cultural and plant protection procedures were followed. The data regarding the growth and yield of tomato were recorded.

Days taken to first flowering after transplanting: First flowering was recorded by measuring the days taken to first flowering after transplanting of five plants randomly selected in each plot.

Plant height (cm): Plant height was recorded by measuring the height of five randomly selected plants in each plot from the ground level to the main apex; mean values were expressed in cm.

Number of branches per plants: Number of branches per plants was recorded by measuring the number of branches per plants of five randomly selected plants in each plot.

Number of fruits per plant: The total number of fruits per plant was counted from each five pre-tagged plant in each plot having.

Days taken to first harvesting (DAT): The fruits harvest per plant was counted from each five pre-tagged plant in each plot having.

Fruits weight (g): Five fruits were selected and weighed from randomly selected tomato plants for each treatment. Tomatoes selected from one treatment were weighed individually and finally the average weight was obtained after all were weighed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth attributes of tomato: Effect of mulching on growth attributes. The two-year pooled data (Table and figure 1) revealed that every mulching treatment had a significantly positive growth characteristic. The data related to growth attributes of tomato are shown in Table and figure 1. The maximum plant height was recorded as 108.84 cm from T₁ treatment using black polythene mulch 30 microns (μm) at the time of harvesting followed by T₆ treatment (Wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) was 106.28 cm. The minimum plant height 95.15 cm respectively was observed for control (T₈ Treatment). The range of plant height was recorder from 95.15 to 108.84cm. The earlier flowering was recorded to T₁ treatment (black polythene mulch 30 microns) 23.30 days. The number of branches per plant was recorded as 10.39 in T₁ treatment (black polythene mulch 30 microns), followed by 10.33 branches per plant in T₂ treatment (silver polyethylene mulch: 25 microns). The increased in plant growth might be due to plastic mulches that provide proper soil temperature and moisture content during the entire growth stage of tomato and create favorable conditions essential for plant processes, which ultimately lead to an increased in photosynthetic capacity and metabolic activities of the plant. This in turn builds a high yield of carbohydrates, which gives rise to cell division and cell enlargement, which induces the growth of the plant (Regar 2017, Islam *et al* 2014 and Maida 2014).

Yield attributes of tomato: Effect of mulching on yield and yield attributes. Yield and yield attributes were significantly affected by different mulch treatments. The two-year pooled data relating to yield and yield characteristics are shown in Table and Figure 2. Among the eight treatments, T₁ treatment (black polyethylene mulch 30 μm) recorded the earliest number of days to harvest, which was found to be the best for days to first harvest (65.70 days). The range of days taken to first harvesting was recorder from 65.70 to 74.50 days.

The two-year pooled data number of fruits plant⁻¹ are shown in Table and Figure 2. The T₆ treatment (wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) recorded significantly highest number of fruits per plant (46.83) followed by T₅ treatment (Wheat straw mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) 46.24. A number of fruits cluster⁻¹ The T₆ treatment (wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) recorded significantly highest number of fruits cluster⁻¹ (7.20) followed by T₄ treatment

(Paddy straw mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) 6.90. The T₆ treatment (wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha⁻¹) was observed to best for Number of fruits plant⁻¹ (46.83 cm), fruit weight (57.40g), fruit yield plant⁻¹ (2.414 kg), fruit yield plot⁻¹ (83.605 kg) and fruit yield ha⁻¹ (69.670 t). Incorporation of wild grass leaves mulch increased yield, it might be due to increase of soil moisture, higher water use efficiency, available water to plants, easily decompose, provide nutrient to soil and plants, higher microbial activity and weed free environment in root zone that helped in better nutrient uptake by plant resulting in better vegetative growth which increased the photosynthesis rate and translocation of photosynthesis from leaves to the fruit (Regar 2017, Thentu *et al.* 2016 and Islam *et al.* 2014).

Table 1: Effect of different type of mulches on growth attributes of tomato.

Treatments	Days taken to first flowering after transplanting			Plant height (cm)								
				15 DAT			30 DAT			45 DAT		
	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled
T ₁ - Black polyethylene mulch: 30 Microns	22.80	23.80	23.30	20.18	18.62	19.40	42.52	35.10	38.81	67.32	58.44	62.88
T ₂ - Silver polyethylene mulch: 25 Microns	24.40	25.40	24.90	21.52	20.00	20.76	39.74	31.86	35.80	64.74	55.82	60.28
T ₃ - Pasture mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	26.80	27.80	27.30	17.66	16.10	16.88	40.12	32.38	36.25	64.48	55.68	60.08
T ₄ - Paddy straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	24.00	25.00	24.50	21.18	19.58	20.38	42.52	34.50	38.51	67.66	58.86	63.26
T ₅ - Wheat straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	23.40	24.40	23.90	21.58	20.06	20.82	42.66	34.60	38.63	67.74	58.92	63.33
T ₆ - Wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	25.60	26.60	26.10	19.78	18.20	18.99	42.84	35.16	39.00	67.52	59.04	63.28
T ₇ - Grass leaves trash (which are used for the cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 t ha ⁻¹	26.80	27.80	27.30	21.04	19.44	20.24	41.72	33.64	37.68	66.58	57.70	62.14
T ₈ - Control: Without mulch	27.20	28.20	27.70	19.54	17.98	18.76	38.66	30.46	34.56	63.40	54.60	59.00

Treatments	Plant height (cm)									Number of branches per plants		
	60 DAT			75 DAT			At the time of harvesting			2024	2025	Pooled
	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled			
T ₁ - Black polyethylene mulch: 30 Microns	88.40	78.52	83.46	99.84	95.30	97.57	119.38	98.30	108.84	10.86	9.92	10.39
T ₂ - Silver polyethylene mulch: 25 Microns	80.38	76.34	78.36	96.74	95.32	96.03	110.80	97.82	104.31	11.04	9.62	10.33
T ₃ - Pasture mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	81.30	71.14	76.22	92.72	87.98	90.35	106.16	91.28	98.72	9.92	8.66	9.29
T ₄ - Paddy straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	94.36	84.36	89.36	97.08	93.00	95.04	115.60	94.60	105.10	10.18	8.98	9.58
T ₅ - Wheat straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	94.84	84.92	89.88	98.68	93.26	95.97	115.46	95.86	105.66	10.58	9.20	9.89
T ₆ - Wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	93.40	82.94	88.17	103.06	96.88	99.97	113.52	99.04	106.28	10.97	9.57	10.27
T ₇ - Grass leaves trash (which are used for the cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 t ha ⁻¹	87.26	77.36	82.31	96.68	93.04	94.86	109.44	94.96	102.20	10.82	9.61	10.22
T ₈ - Control: Without mulch	85.32	65.98	75.65	94.26	88.90	91.58	100.32	89.98	95.15	8.93	7.86	8.40

Table 2: Effect of different type of mulches on yield and yield attributes of tomato.

Treatments	Number of fruits per plants			Days taken to first harvesting (DAT)			Fruits weight (g)			Number of fruits per cluster		
	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled
T ₁ - Black polyethylene mulch: 30 Microns	42.87	37.04	39.96	64.60	66.80	65.70	54.60	52.80	53.70	5.80	4.40	5.10
T ₂ - Silver polyethylene mulch: 25 Microns	40.75	35.17	37.96	65.60	68.20	66.90	52.60	50.40	51.50	6.20	4.80	5.50
T ₃ - Pasture mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	48.72	41.26	44.99	69.80	73.20	71.50	51.40	49.00	50.20	6.40	5.00	5.70
T ₄ - Paddy straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	47.97	40.39	44.18	66.00	68.80	67.40	54.60	53.00	53.80	7.80	6.00	6.90
T ₅ - Wheat straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	49.78	42.69	46.24	68.60	71.60	70.10	57.40	56.00	56.70	7.20	5.80	6.50
T ₆ - Wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	50.66	43.00	46.83	64.80	67.20	66.00	58.00	56.80	57.40	8.00	6.40	7.20
T ₇ - Grass leaves trash (which are used for the	41.92	36.46	39.19	69.60	72.80	71.20	54.60	52.60	53.60	6.40	5.20	5.80

cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 t ha ⁻¹												
T ₈ - Control: Without mulch	36.77	31.09	33.93	72.80	76.20	74.50	48.40	45.60	47.00	4.20	3.40	3.80

Treatments	Fruits yield per plants (kg)			Fruits yield per plot (kg)			Fruits yield per ha (t)		
	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled	2024	2025	Pooled
T ₁ - Black polyethylene mulch: 30 Microns	2.080	1.495	1.788	72.08	53.09	62.585	60.07	44.24	52.155
T ₂ - Silver polyethylene mulch: 25 Microns	2.284	1.804	2.044	78.71	64.23	71.470	65.59	53.53	59.560
T ₃ - Pasture mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	1.939	1.279	1.609	67.12	46.04	56.580	55.94	38.37	47.155
T ₄ - Paddy straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	2.472	1.946	2.209	84.90	67.94	76.420	70.75	56.62	63.685
T ₅ - Wheat straw mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	2.440	1.865	2.153	84.16	65.91	75.035	70.13	54.93	62.530
T ₆ - Wild grass leaves mulch: 10 t ha ⁻¹	2.660	2.167	2.414	91.72	75.49	83.605	76.43	62.91	69.670
T ₇ - Grass leaves trash (which are used for the cow/buffalo to sleep at night): 10 t ha ⁻¹	2.318	1.160	1.739	80.00	40.11	60.055	66.67	33.43	50.050
T ₈ - Control: Without mulch	1.491	0.887	1.189	51.46	31.74	41.600	42.88	26.45	34.665

Fig 1: Effect of different type of mulches on growth attributes of tomato.

Fig 2: Effect of different type of mulches on yield and yield attributes of tomato.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the experiment, it can be concluded that the different mulches performed better than the control. It was found that the application of black polyethylene mulch (30 µm) was the best treatment among all growth characteristics. Thus, it is inferred that the use of black polyethylene mulch (30 microns) was found to be more effective in terms of tomato growth. It was found that application of wild grass leaves mulch (10 ton ha⁻¹) was the best treatment among all yield attributes except days taken to first harvesting, which was highest observed in black polyethylene mulch (30 µm). Thus, it was inferred that the usage of wild grass leaves mulch (10 ton hectare⁻¹) was found to be both more effective and economically viable in terms of yield of tomato. therefore Incorporation of grass leaves mulch increased yield, it might be due to increase of soil moisture, higher water use efficiency, available water to plants, easily decompose, provide nutrient to soil and plants, higher microbial activity and weed free environment in root zone that helped in better nutrient uptake by plant resulting in better vegetative growth which increased the photosynthesis rate and translocation of photosynthesis from leaves to the fruit.

The results of this study exhibited the significant effect of biological mulches during the growing season and inanimate mulch during the yield season. The biological and inanimate mulches reduce soil water evaporation and improved soil water availability. Using biological and inanimate mulches produced a more vigorous plant, number of more flowers and fruits, earlier and higher yield and increased soil temperature as compared to without mulch. Using inanimate mulches produced a more vigorous plant, earlier flowers, maximum plant height, early harvesting and higher number of branches compared to biological mulch and without mulch. While using biological mulch resulted in more fruit, fruit weight and yield increased compared to inanimate mulch and no mulch. The marketable yield was also greater with the use of biological mulches. The increase in yield of biological and inanimate mulched was probably associated with the conservation of moisture, improved microclimate both beneath and above the soil surface, light reflection and great weed control. Under biological and inanimate mulches increased soil microbial biomass carbon. Mulching facilitates retention of soil moisture and improved physical, chemical and biological properties of soil. Mulching suppresses weed growth, protects the upper fertile soil from erosion, and minimizes variation in soil temperature.

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